

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH AND OTHER FOREIGN LANGUAGES

¹Akhmedova Zulayho, ²Berdieva Zamona

^{1,2}Ministry of Internal Affairs, Kashkadarya Academic Lyceum

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Abstract. *This article discusses methods of teaching English and other foreign languages, modern technologies used in teaching English, and popularization of English among young people.*

Keywords: *multimedia, english language, pedagogue, teaching methodology, foreign language popularization, modern methods, pedagogy, best practice.*

INTRODUCTION

On May 19, 2022, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the popularization of learning foreign languages to a new level in terms of quality" aimed at increasing the quality and scope of teaching foreign languages, including English, in our country" decision was taken. In order to coordinate work in this regard, the Agency for Popularization of Foreign Language Learning was established under the Cabinet of Ministers. Although the agency has not yet started its activities, effective and systematic work is being done to popularize the study of foreign languages. Applying advanced experiences and achievements of pedagogy to education is one of the important conditions of today. Currently, a huge base of experience has been formed, which the teacher can use during his work and it is getting richer every day. But still, it is difficult for teachers and future professionals to master these experiences. The teacher's role in creating best practice and popularizing it among colleagues is of particular importance. Educators should consider the cost and effectiveness of new pedagogical practices. The orientation of the teacher's practical activity to innovation allows the practical application of the achievements achieved as a result of theoretical pedagogical research. In order to popularize the results of such studies, it is necessary to introduce them to the general public. Such news can be delivered to representatives of other pedagogies by experts in the field giving quick advice, conducting trainings at special seminars, lecturing at conferences, giving a series of lectures to future pedagogues.

Today, students and young people pay attention to his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose the methods and forms of organizing educational activities that are most suitable for the determined goal of personal development of students. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Popular methods of teaching and learning English, Internet resources were used in the research process. In the process of writing the article, theoretical-deductive conclusion, analysis and synthesis, principles of logic were used. The task of the teacher is to create conditions for the practical acquisition of the language by each student, to allow each student to show his activity and creativity. is the choice of educational methods. The task of the teacher is to activate the student's knowledge activity in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical

technologies, such as collaborative teaching, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualize teaching taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning and mastery will help ensure differentiation. Forms of working with computer educational programs in foreign language classes include: vocabulary learning; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologue speech; teaching writing; development of grammatical phenomena. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information: regional geographical materials, youth life news, articles in newspapers and magazines, etc. can be solved: the ability to build reading skills and use global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work is aimed at studying the possibilities of Internet technologies for expanding the worldview of schoolchildren, establishing and maintaining business relations and relations with their peers in English-speaking countries. Students participate in online tests, quizzes, contests, Olympiads; correspond with their peers in other countries, chat, videoconference, etc. Students can learn about a problem they are currently working on in a project.

The machine can be "friendly" with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you get bored. In this sense, the use of computers can be most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence; all other goals (education, upbringing, development) are realized in the process of realizing this main goal. The communicative approach includes the formation of communication skills and intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the number and size of participants. By participating in a foreign language class, we will create a real communication model for him. Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanism of education are of priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach the ability to navigate freely in a foreign language environment and respond appropriately to different situations, that is, communication. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of authenticity of communication). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error. Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at consciously understanding the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that makes it possible to distinguish this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its purpose is to make students interested in learning foreign language by gathering and expanding knowledge and experience. One of the main requirements for teaching

foreign languages using Internet resources is interaction in the lesson and to create a mystery that is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and completing communicative goals and resulting actions through the medium of speech." By teaching real language, the Internet helps to develop speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real-life situations, but also forces students to respond appropriately to them in a foreign language. One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method, which is a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoproject, collective, oral, concrete, written and internet projects in actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. I believe that project-based education teaches children to cooperate, and cooperative learning instills moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, develops creativity, and activates students. In general, in the process of teaching the project, teaching and learning are inseparable. The project method develops students' communication skills, behavioral culture, the ability to form ideas briefly and easily, the ability to tolerate the opinions of communication partners, the ability to obtain information from various sources, processes using modern computer technologies, and creates a language environment helps the emergence of natural needs in foreign language communication.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Natural and social phenomena are interconnected and develop in a continuous relationship. Since the sciences are reflections of objective reality, none of them exists in isolation from the others. At the same time, the phenomenon and the object can be a source of research for many sciences, for example, the social phenomenon "language" can be studied from its own point of view by linguistics (linguistics), spiritual science (psychology), studies pedagogy (didactics)."

The term "foreign language methodology" is in people's minds as follows, that is, association creates "connection": first of all, to teach the language focused method and set of methodical methods is understood or scientific knowledge about teaching methods, and finally, independent pedagogical science comes to mind. The methodology of foreign language teaching has developed in harmony with didactics. It is undoubtedly known to all of us that the teaching theories of all educational subjects are based on didactics science and receive scientific nutrition from it. Foreign language teaching is also based on didactics.

General theory of didactic education, Methodology is the science of teaching a specific subject, linguodidactics is the general theory of language teaching, and linguomethodology is the science of teaching a specific language. The term "method" refers to the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and worldview in students' teacher-pedagogue in the way of formation and creation of knowledge opportunities and means the student's work method. This concept has countless definitions. The application of methods in foreign language teaching began a long time ago, while principles are relatively new methodological terms. Historically, the methods were grouped into four groups, and their names were called "translation", "correct", "comparative", "and mixed".

In the methodology of foreign language teaching, the expression of intercultural communication is widespread is being used. We can apply this concept in different contexts.

Actually: Intercultural communication - different culture communication-information about the social origin, mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions, value system, etc. of its representatives. In this process, students are introduced to the culture of the country being studied respect, patience and proper understanding of the culture of another country it is necessary to educate and develop in the spirit.

Every foreign language lesson is a cultural intersection, a practice of intercultural communication. Because every word in a foreign language in this process reflects the life and culture of a foreign country. The task before the teachers is the student and to develop students' ability to communicate. For this, training manuals that teach people to communicate effectively and four speech activities in a foreign language are aimed at development. It is necessary to master new methods of education.

CONCLUSION

The form of project work is one of the most relevant technologies that allow students to apply the accumulated knowledge on the subject. Students expand their worldview, the limits of knowledge of the language, gain experience in its practical use, learn to listen and hear speech in a foreign language, and understand each other when defending projects.

Children work with reference books, dictionaries, computers, and thus create the possibility of direct contact with the real language, which does not provide language learning in the classroom only with the help of textbooks. Working on a project is a creative process. The student searches for a solution to the problem independently or under the guidance of the teacher, which requires not only knowledge of the language, but also a large amount of scientific knowledge, creative, communicative and intellectual abilities. In the process of learning foreign languages, the project method can be used as part of the program materials on almost any subject.

Working on projects develops imagination, fantasy, creative thinking, independence and other personal qualities. Modern technologies are also used. The main idea is to create conditions for active joint activity of students in various educational conditions. Children are put into groups of 3-4 people; they are given one task, in which everyone's role is discussed. Each student is responsible not only for the result of his work, but also for the result of the whole group. That's why weak students try to find out what they don't understand from weak ones, and strong students try to understand the task thoroughly. And the whole class benefits because the gaps are closed together.

The introduction of information technologies into education greatly diversifies the process of information perception and processing. Thanks to the computer, the Internet and multimedia, a unique opportunity has been created for students to master a large amount of data with further analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of educational activity is also expanding significantly. In the context of using multimedia, students receive information from newspapers, television, have conversations and hold teleconferences.

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